

Spectral and biocidal studies of manganese(II), dioxomolybdenum(VI) and oxovanadium(V) complexes with monobasic bidentate Schiff base ligands

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Abstract : Schiff base complexes of manganese(II), dioxomolybdenum(VI) and oxovanadium(V) derived from 1*H*-indol-2,3-dione and 5-nitro-1*H*-indol-2,3-dione and 2-aminobenzenethiol have been characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, molecular weight determinations and spectral studies including IR, ¹H NMR, UV, ESR and X-ray studies. The spectroscopic results show the involvement of sulphur and azomethine nitrogen in coordination to the central metal ion. The magnetic moment values of the manganese(II) complexes are in the range of 5.80–6.15 B.M. suggesting a high spin state of manganese in these complexes. Based on the spectral studies, tetrahedral geometry for the manganese(II) complexes and octahedral geometry for the dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes have been proposed. In the case of the oxovanadium(V) complexes, vanadium is in penta- or hexa-coordinated environments. Antimicrobial effects of some representative ligands and their complexes on different species of pathogenic fungi and bacteria have also been recorded. Further, the complexes were tested for their antifertility activity.

Keywords : Manganese(II), Schiff base ligand, dioxomolybdenum(VI), oxovanadium(V).

Introduction

Transition metal complexes derived from sulphur donor ligands have wide applicability, ranging from synthesis to application in diverse fields¹. Over the last more than one decade, there has been a dramatic growth of interest in inorganic complexes based materials that exhibit unusual properties. Some sulphur and nitrogen containing ligands and their complexes have been found to be important precursor for semiconducting materials¹ used as photosensitizer for conversion of light energy to electricity². Several Schiff base complexes have been synthesised as models for some of these metalloproteins³⁻⁷. A large number of stable and accessible oxidation states and coordination numbers render molybdenum to be a versatile transition element. The oxomolybdenum complexes with ligands containing hard soft ONS donor atoms are of importance⁸.

Recently interest in multidentate O and N donor ligand complexes of vanadium(V) has increased because of their insulin mimetic properties. The model chemistry of haloperoxidases and catalytic chemistry with potential practical applications are also of interest⁹⁻¹². Oxovanadium(IV) and (V) complexes, especially with bi and tridentate chelating ligands bound to the metal mainly via oxygen and

nitrogen atoms have being extensively investigated with respect to their remarkable efficiency as insulin mimetic compounds¹³⁻¹⁵. Their use as orally active medicaments would represent an important advance in the treatment of human diabetes mellitus. Other studies involving potential applications of oxovanadium complexes have also been performed, with emphasis, for e.g. in their antitumor¹⁶ and antibacterial activity¹⁷. The bioactivity of heterocyclic Schiff bases as well as of their metal complexes is of interest, especially due to their pharmacological properties. The coordination chemistry of vanadium has attracted considerable attention of bioinorganic and coordination chemists because of the discovery of enzymatic^{18,19} and physiological activity²⁰⁻²². The inherent biological potential of sulphur donor ligands prompted us to prepare manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes of benzothiazolines. Benzothiazolines constitute an important class of sulphur donor ligands. Benzothiazolines with N[∧]S donor system have been shown to be active against viruses, protozoa, smallpox and certain kinds of tumors²³.

In the present paper we report the synthesis, characterization and biological activity of these complexes with biologically active monobasic bidentate benzothiazolines derived from heterocyclic ketones.

Table 1. Analytical data and physical properties of the ligands and their complexes

Compd.	Colour	Melting point (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)						Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)
			N	S	Cl	Mn	Mo	V	
Bzt ₁ H	Yellow	126	10.84 (11.01)	12.11 (12.61)	-	-	-	-	235 (254)
Bzt ₂ H	Green	153	13.91 (14.04)	10.16 (10.71)	-	-	-	-	286 (299)
[MnCl(Bzt ₁)H ₂ O]	Light yellow	202	7.63 (7.74)	8.77 (8.86)	9.73 (9.80)	15.12 (15.19)	-	-	346 (361)
[Mn(Bzt ₁) ₂]	Light yellow	210	9.81 (9.98)	11.36 (11.42)	-	9.67 (9.78)	-	-	552 (561)
[MnCl(Bzt ₂)H ₂ O]	Reddish brown	244	10.21 (10.33)	7.78 (7.88)	8.65 (8.72)	13.48 (13.51)	-	-	394 (406)
[Mn(Bzt ₂) ₂]	Reddish brown	256	12.74 (12.88)	9.71 (9.82)	-	8.38 (8.42)	-	-	641 (652)
[MoO ₂ (Bzt ₁) ₂]	Reddish brown	264	8.16 (8.83)	10.07 (10.11)	-	-	15.10 (15.12)	-	627 (634)
[MoO ₂ (Bzt ₂) ₂]	Black	268	11.43 (11.58)	8.69 (8.84)	-	-	13.11 (13.22)	-	709 (725)
[VOCl ₂ (Bzt ₁)]	Dark green	205	7.07 (7.16)	8.16 (8.20)	18.08 (18.13)	-	-	13.01 (13.02)	383 (391)
[VOCl(Bzt ₁) ₂]	Yellowish green	209	9.15 (9.20)	10.14 (10.53)	5.73 (5.82)	-	-	8.33 (8.36)	593 (608)
[VOCl ₂ (Bzt ₂)]	Mustard yellow	236	9.59 (9.63)	7.18 (7.35)	16.17 (16.26)	-	-	11.63 (11.68)	425 (436)
[VOCl(Bzt ₂) ₂]	Mustard yellow	248	12.01 (12.02)	9.12 (9.17)	5.01 (5.07)	-	-	7.24 (7.29)	684 (698)

D and E received same doses of manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes, for the same period.

The fertility test of individual rats was done before the experiment and after 55 days of the experiment. Each rat was cohabited with progesterone female in 1 : 2 ratios. Vaginal smear was examined every morning for positive mating and number of litters delivered were recorded. The rats were sacrificed within 24 h after the last administration of the compounds, i.e. on 61th days of the experiment. The testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate were removed, fat was cleared, before weighing. Sperm motility and sperm density were assayed in cauda epididymis and testes. The parts of testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate from each rat were kept at -20 °C until assayed for protein, sialic acid, cholesterol and fructose. Student 't' test was used for the assessment of the significance of variation and the data are presented as mean ± 5 EM²⁸.

Results and discussion

The 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar reactions of MnCl₂.4H₂O with the monobasic bidentate ligands have been carried out in methanol. The successive replacement of chloride resulted in the formation of products [MnCl(N[^]S)H₂O] and [Mn(N[^]S)₂]. These reactions can be represented by the following general equations,

(where N[^]S represents the donor system of the benzothiazoline)

The reactions of dioxobis(2,4-pentanedinato)-molybdenum(VI) with the ligands were carried out in 1 : 2 molar ratios in dry methanol. The reactions proceed with the liberation of two molecules of 2,4-pentanedione. The resulting coloured solids are diamagnetic.

Vanadium oxytrichloride reacts with one or two equivalents of the sodium salts of the ligands in anhydrous methanol and successive replacement of chloride gives products of the types [VOCl₂(N[^]S)] and [VOCl(N[^]S)₂].

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The reactions in a 1 : 3 molar ratios were also attempted, but even on prolonged heating did not proceed beyond the replacement of two chlorine atoms by the ligand moieties, and [VOCl(N[^]S)₂] type of derivatives were the end products. The complexes are soluble in methanol, DMF and DMSO and sparingly soluble in H₂O. The molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in dry DMF lie in the 10–15 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ range, indicating that they are non-electrolytes.

Spectral studies :

UV spectra :

The electronic spectra of the free ligands consist of two bands in the region 250–270 nm and 300–325 nm characteristics of the benzothiazolines. These bands arising out of φ-φ* and π-π* benzenoid transitions remain unaltered in the complexes, whereas an additional band is also observed in the 370–395 nm range due to the n-π* electronic transitions of the azomethine which indicates the isomerization of the ligands on complexation. All the complexes show an absorption maximum in the region 450–580 nm in the visible region, which probably arises from ligand to metal charge transfer.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of the benzothiazolines display band due to νNH at 3300–3250 cm⁻¹ which disappears in the spectra of the complexes and thus showing the deprotonation of this functional group and subsequent binding of nitrogen with the metal atom. Further in the case of the metal complexes, a strong band around 1600 cm⁻¹ may be ascribed to the coordinated ν(C=N) group and this very well supports the fact that the resulting complexes are metal imine derivatives, as the benzothiazoline ring rearranges to give the imine which finally acts as monofunctional bidentate ligands. The coordination of the ligands through the azomethine nitrogen and the thio-sulphur is further supported by the appearance of new bands of medium to weak intensity in the regions 485–380, 360–295 and 380–285 cm⁻¹ due to νM←N, νM-S

and ν_{M-Cl} vibrations, respectively. In the spectra of the 1 : 1 manganese complexes, a band observed at $895-670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ that can be assigned to the coordinated H_2O molecule. This band is absent in the case of 1 : 2 complexes. In case of dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes, new bands observed in the regions $920-910\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $900-980\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ indicating a *cis*- MoO_2 structure. Further the appearance of a strong band in the $940-985\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region in the oxovanadium(V) complexes may be assigned to $\text{V}=\text{O}$ stretching vibration.

ESR spectra :

The electronic spin resonance spectra of the manganese(II) complexes were recorded at the room temperature. These consist of a single broad peak in each case, from which the lande splitting factor ('g' values) has been calculated. The 'g' values for the complexes lie in the range 2.00–2.09 indicating a tetra-coordinated geometry for these complexes²⁹.

NMR spectra :

The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the free ligands and their derivatives were recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$. The signals of the NH proton at δ 5.59 to 4.15 ppm in benzothiazolines are found to be absent in their metal complexes confirming the deprotonation of NH group and coordination of metal with the nitrogen atom. The aromatic protons in case of the ligands and its complexes appear in the range δ 6.21–8.88 ppm.

^{13}C NMR spectra :

The ^{13}C NMR spectral data also support the authenticity of the proposed structures. The considerable shifts in the position of carbon atoms adjacent to the azomethine nitrogen (δ 153.24–156.14 ppm) and thiolic sulphur (δ 156.72–164.15 ppm) support the proposed coordination in the complexes. Thus, the shifts in the positions of carbon atoms adjacent to the coordinating atom clearly indicate the bonding of the azomethine nitrogen and thiolic sulphur to the molybdenum atom.

X-Ray diffraction :

The X-ray diffraction analysis of the compound $[\text{Mn}(\text{Bzt}_1)_2]$ confirms the orthorhombic crystal system for this derivative with the unit cell dimensions as $a = 25.774$, $b = 17.543$ and $c = 10.298$ with $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$ respectively. Miller indices h , k and l have been assigned to each 'd' value and 2θ angles are reported in Table 2. On the basis of these spectral studies for the

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction data of the $[\text{MnCl}(\text{Bzt}_1)_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ complex

Peak no.	2θ (deg.) (obs.)	h	k	l	d -spacing (obs.) (Å)
1	15.37	2	2	0	7.249
2	16.93	3	0	1	6.591
3	22.60	5	1	0	4.942
4	25.82	4	3	0	4.331
5	27.45	5	2	1	4.081
6	30.75	3	4	1	3.652
7	31.93	3	3	2	3.521
8	37.92	7	3	1	2.981
9	42.22	4	3	3	2.692
10	44.63	10	1	0	2.550
11	46.34	2	7	0	2.462
12	48.21	8	5	0	2.373

$$a = 25.774, b = 17.543 \text{ and } c = 10.298, \alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ.$$

manganese and dioxomolybdenum complexes, the tetrahedral and octahedral geometry, respectively, have been suggested whereas, in case of oxovanadium(V) complexes, vanadium atom was found in penta- and hexa-coordinated states (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Proposed structure of the complexes.

Antimicrobial activity :

The synthesized ligands and their corresponding metal complexes were tested against pathogenic fungi, viz. *Macrophomina phaseolina*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and bacteria, viz. *Bacillus subtilis*, *Klebsiella aerogenus*. Here also the sulphur containing compounds inhibit the growth of the fungus under the test to a greater extent than the other compounds. This is because sulphur has vacant *d* orbitals and has also lone pair of electrons. It is important to note that the metal chelates exhibit more inhibitory effects than the parent ligands. The increased lipophilic

Table 3. Antifungal screening data for the ligands and their complexes

Compd.	Inhibition after 96 h (conc. in ppm)					
	<i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i>			<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>		
	50	100	200	50	100	200
Bzt ₁ H	29	44	59	41	54	66
Bzt ₂ H	23	32	53	32	37	45
[MnCl(Bzt ₁)H ₂ O]	32	51	64	45	59	69
[Mn(Bzt ₁) ₂]	36	58	67	48	64	76
[MnCl(Bzt ₂)H ₂ O]	26	37	56	36	41	57
[Mn(Bzt ₂) ₂]	31	43	62	38	46	62
[MoO ₂ (Bzt ₁) ₂]	34	47	67	44	58	76
[MoO ₂ (Bzt ₂) ₂]	36	41	58	37	43	51
[VOCl ₂ (Bzt ₁)]	33	48	64	46	59	72
[VOCl(Bzt ₁) ₂]	45	59	78	58	68	83
[VOCl ₂ (Bzt ₂)]	39	42	62	43	52	68
[VOCl(Bzt ₂) ₂]	55	69	84	56	64	86
Bavistin	84	100	100	87	100	100
(Standard)						

Table 4. Antibacterial screening data for the ligands and their complexes

Compd.	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm) after 24 h (conc. in ppm)			
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>		<i>Klebsiella aerogenus</i>	
	500	1000	500	1000
Bzt ₁ H	4	5	3	6
Bzt ₂ H	3	4	5	8
[MnCl(Bzt ₁)H ₂ O]	7	9	5	8
[Mn(Bzt ₁) ₂]	8	10	7	11
[MnCl(Bzt ₂)H ₂ O]	5	6	9	12
[Mn(Bzt ₂) ₂]	7	8	11	14
[MoO ₂ (Bzt ₁) ₂]	9	10	12	13
[MoO ₂ (Bzt ₂) ₂]	7	12	8	11
[VOCl ₂ (Bzt ₁)]	6	9	5	8
[VOCl(Bzt ₁) ₂]	8	10	7	10
[VOCl ₂ (Bzt ₂)]	5	9	8	15
[VOCl(Bzt ₂) ₂]	6	12	9	16
Streptomycin	18	19	17	20
(Standard)				

character of these complexes seems to be responsible for their enhanced biological potency²⁹. Mode of action of antimicrobials may involve various targets in microorganisms, e.g. interferences with the cell wall synthesis, damage to the cytoplasmic membrane as a result of which cell permeability may be altered, or they may disorganise the lipoproteins leading to cell death³⁰ (Tables 3 and 4).

Antifertility activity :

Experiments were conducted *in vivo* on male rats to check antifertility activity. The results reported are as follows :

Body and organ weights :

Administration of benzothiazoline of 5-nitro-1*H*-indol-2,3-dione and its manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes did not cause any significant change in the body weights of the treated rats. The weights of the testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate were reduced significantly when compared with the vehicle treated control (Table 5).

Sperm motility and sperm density :

A sharp decline ($P \leq 0.001$) in the sperm motility was noticed in the rats treated with benzothiazoline of 5-nitro-1*H*-indol-2,3-dione and its manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes. Sperm density in the cauda epididymis was also reduced significantly ($P \leq 0.001$) in all treated groups (Table 6).

Table 5. Changes in the body weight and weights of the reproductive organs after the treatment with the ligand and its manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes

Group	Treatment	Body weight (g)		Organ weights [mg/100 g body weight]			
		Initial	Final	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Ventral prostate
A	Control	175.0±4.60	195.0±5.0	1450.0±20.5	480.0±5.9	490.0±10.5	395.0±10.8
B	Bzt ₂ H	184.0±6.50	209.0±5.0 ^c	1215.0±12.5 ^b	430.0±6.9 ^b	435.0±5.7 ^b	285.0±11.4 ^b
C	[Mn(Bzt ₂) ₂]	171.0±6.30	201.0±9.86 ^c	1010.0±13.9 ^b	295.0±5.7 ^b	310.0±9.8 ^b	210.0±11.6 ^b
D	[MoO ₂ (Bzt ₂) ₂]	182.0±7.50	204.0±8.50 ^c	985.0±10.5 ^b	285.0±7.5 ^b	320.0±6.9 ^b	220.0±10.7 ^b
E	[VOCl(Bzt ₂) ₂]	177.0±6.80	207.0±6.0 ^c	920.0±12.8 ^b	270.0±6.5 ^b	295.0±7.6 ^b	195.0±7.9 ^b

Values means ±5 EM of six determinations.

Group B compared with group A.

Groups C, D and E compared with group B.

a = *P* ≤ 0.05, *b* = *P* < 0.001, *c* = NS, non-significant.

Table 6. Effects of the ligand and its manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes on sperm motility, concentration and fertility in rats

Group	Treatment	Sperm motility (%) Cauda epididymis	Sperm motility (%)		Fertility (%)
			Testes	Cauda epididymis	
A	Control	78.0 ± 2.50	4.60 ± 0.23	49.70 ± 2.59	100 (+ve)
B	Bzt ₂ H	55.0 ± 2.8 ^b	2.95 ± 0.20 ^b	25.0 ± 3.10 ^b	75 (-ve)
C	[Mn(Bzt ₂) ₂]	36.0 ± 2.8 ^b	1.95 ± 0.15 ^b	10.60 ± 2.10 ^b	91.8 (-ve)
D	[MoO ₂ (Bzt ₂) ₂]	38.0 ± 3.3 ^b	1.85 ± 0.17 ^b	9.70 ± 2.30 ^b	95.0 (-ve)
E	[VOCl(Bzt ₂) ₂]	32.0 ± 5.7 ^b	1.75 ± 0.17 ^b	9.90 ± 2.10 ^b	92.0 (-ve)

Values means ±5 EM of six determinations.

Group B compared with group A.

Groups C, D and E compared with group B.

a = *P* ≤ 0.05, *b* = *P* < 0.001.

Tissue biochemistry :

Protein and sialic acid :

Protein and sialic acid contents in testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate were significantly decreased after the treatment with the ligand and its manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes (Table 7).

Testicular cholesterol :

Testicular cholesterol was increased significantly (*P* ≤ 0.001) after the treatment with the ligand and its manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes (Table 7).

Fructose :

Fructose contents of seminal vesicle was decreased (*P* ≤ 0.001) in rats treated with the ligand and its manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes (Table 7).

Discussion

In the present study a significant decrease was ob-

served in the weight of testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate after the treatment with the ligand and its manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes. Significant decrease in testes weight may be due to the decrease in the number of spermatogenic elements and spermatogonia³¹ that is cell death which leads to regression of these organs³² and suggest the reduced availability of the androgens³³.

Treatment with the ligand and its manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes resulted in the sharp decline in the sperm motility of cauda epididymis. On the other hand the low caudal epididymal sperm density may be due to the alteration in the androgen metabolism³⁴.

The low motility and negative fertility test may be attributed to the lack of the forward progression and reduction in the density of spermatozoa and altered biochemical milieu of cauda epididymis. Treatment with the various complexes also alters the biochemical parameters

Table 7. Tissue biochemistry of the ligand (Bz₂H) and its manganese, molybdenum and vanadium complexes

Group	Treatment	Protein (mg/g)					Sialic acid (mg/g)					Testicular cholesterol (mg/g)	Seminal Vesicle fructose (mg/g)
		Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Ventral prostate	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Ventral prostate	Ventral prostate			
A	Control	235.0 ± 7.14	205.0 ± 6.70	195.0 ± 6.50	180.0 ± 3.50	4.90 ± 0.35	5.30 ± 0.39	5.40 ± 0.37	5.70 ± 0.45	5.70 ± 0.45	7.60 ± 0.72	450.0 ± 30.0	
B	Bz ₂ H	190.0 ± 6.50 ^b	175.0 ± 4.85 ^b	150.0 ± 4.65 ^a	150.0 ± 3.15 ^b	4.15 ± 0.30 ^a	4.24 ± 0.40 ^b	4.41 ± 0.38 ^b	4.65 ± 0.43 ^a	4.65 ± 0.43 ^a	8.52 ± 0.40 ^b	395.0 ± 25.0 ^a	
C	[Mn(Bz ₂) ₂]	140.0 ± 6.75 ^b	130.0 ± 5.65 ^b	138.0 ± 4.35 ^a	110.0 ± 3.95 ^b	3.45 ± 0.32 ^b	3.25 ± 0.38 ^b	3.15 ± 0.33 ^b	3.85 ± 0.15 ^b	3.85 ± 0.15 ^b	9.65 ± 0.30 ^b	315.0 ± 27.0 ^b	
D	[MoO ₂ (Bz ₂) ₂]	140.0 ± 6.95 ^b	135.0 ± 4.75 ^b	125.0 ± 3.95 ^b	115.0 ± 4.15 ^b	3.20 ± 0.34 ^b	3.20 ± 0.37 ^b	3.43 ± 0.32 ^b	3.53 ± 0.20 ^b	3.53 ± 0.20 ^b	9.85 ± 0.29 ^b	310.0 ± 31.0 ^b	
E	[VOCl(Bz ₂) ₂]	135.0 ± 4.75 ^b	140.0 ± 4.45 ^b	118.0 ± 3.60 ^b	109.0 ± 4.30 ^b	2.90 ± 0.45 ^b	3.1 ± 0.28 ^b	3.8 ± 0.42 ^b	3.30 ± 0.22 ^b	3.30 ± 0.22 ^b	9.70 ± 0.12 ^b	285.0 ± 25.0 ^b	

Values means ± 5 EM of six determinations.
 Group B compared with group A.
 Groups C, D and E compared with group B.
 a = P ≤ 0.05.

of the reproductive tract. Reduction in sialic acid contents in testes, epididymis, ventral prostate and seminal vesicle in treated rats may be correlated with the loss of the androgen³⁴. Reduced contents of the proteins in testes and sex accessory organs, may probably be due to the absence of spermatogenic stages in the testes. A significant increase of testicular cholesterol indicates that pituitary gonadotropins may not be available for steroidogenesis³⁴. Our study suggest that addition of manganese, molybdenum or vanadium moiety to the ligand enhances its activity and the compounds of molybdenum are more effective in regulating the fertility in male rats.

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